

SCHOOL PRINCIPALS' ADMINISTRATIVE CHARACTERISTICS AND THE EFFECTS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTSⁱ

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Abstract:

This study aiming to determine the managerial characteristics of the school principals and to reveal the effects on the development of the students was planned in a qualitative case study model. The study group was 16 undergraduate students. The semi-structured letters were used as a means of collecting data in this study written by undergraduate students to the school principals. The findings were analyzed by using content analysis technique. The findings show that school principals exhibit both positive and negative personal characteristics. The most frequent positive personal characteristics of the school principals were good-humored, neat, sympathetic, fair, tolerant, and respectful. The most frequent negative personal characteristics were authoritarian, punitive, normative, strict, and distant attitudes. The school principals exhibit positive administrative features such as to display solution-focused management, to create positive school culture, to make staff feel valuable, and to listen everybody as carefully as. School principals also exhibit negative administrative characteristics such as punitive attitude, extreme restrictive attitude, a distant attitude, and to behave official. The most frequent instructional leadership characteristics of school principals were to focus on educational success of the school, to motivate to learn, to care all students to establish an effective learning environment, to lead to teaching and to appreciate success of students. The positive attitudes of school principals ensure the feelings on students such as self-confidence, self-respect, feel precious, gratitude, awareness, love and courage. The negative attitudes ensure the feelings such as fear, violence, humiliation, lack of self-confidence, lack of motivation, and timidity. Based on the findings it can be suggested that school principals should consider the effects of positive administrative attitudes on the development of students.

Keywords: school principal, administrative characteristics, student, development

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1. Introduction

Education system is in the focus of interest of all social groups due to the direct effects on the economic, social, cultural and political development of the countries and the life quality of people. In different countries, a number of different methods are used to evaluate the development of the education system, and the success of schools, school principals, teachers and students. In these evaluations it is generally aimed to improve school leadership and teaching practices, as well as to ensure information to the parents and the society about the outputs of the school education by determining the success of the whole education system. In this context, it is very important to determine the effects of the school principals' administrative skills on the development of students.

In last two decades, according to the production-oriented approach, the success of the education systems are assessed depending on the schools' academic performance, therefore it is generally focused on the academic success of students rather than the requirements of them (Cheesman, Simpson and Wint, 2006; Haahr, 2005; Marcotte and Hemelt, 2007; Wenglinsky, 2001). The schools are also seen as the competitive organizations requiring sustained success and so the school principals are forced to display the leadership skills to fulfill these requirements (Incel, 2005). Therefore, the school principal is expected to manage school in line with to meet the aims of education system by fulfilling different responsibilities (Pehlivan-Aydın, 2002). Actually, the students, teachers and managers bring their beliefs and values into the school environment as well as their individual aims and the needs. A school principal should support to shape the perception, attitudes and beliefs of these individuals in the school as well as to create an effective organizational culture (Hoy and Miskel, 2010). A school principal who is also in the focus of different tendencies and expectations stemmed from different social groups can only fulfill these expectations in cooperation with these social forces (Aydın, 2010).

School effectiveness studies focus on the student outcomes, in general. A school that is more effective than the others is generally defined as a school that brings the basic qualities of students to a better than predicted level (Day and Sammons, 2013). Blase and Blase (1999) define an effective school in which the school principals have important responsibilities such as to focus on teaching and learning activities as an instructional leader, to support teachers' collaborative efforts, to pioneer the development of coaching relationships among teachers, to encourage and support the reorganization of the curricula. In addition, the studies conducted by Murphy (1998), Spillane (2003), Şişman and Turan (2004) reveal that school administrators' main responsibility is to improve teaching programs and teaching-learning processes and to focus on the success of teachers and students. Effective principals work relentlessly to improve student achievement by focusing on the quality of instruction in school (Portin, Schneider, DeArmond and Gundlach, 2003). According to Akpan (2016), and Balci (2001), the priority of school principals should be to establish a learning environment that allows cognitive, emotional, psychomotor, social and aesthetic development of the

students. In other words, they must ensure the developments of the students by fulfilling the administrative responsibilities, adequately.

Since the main purpose for school principals is to increase the quality of education in the school, they must have personal, administrative and professional competences in order to be able to fulfill this aim effectively (Şahin, 2011). Actually, either insufficient administrative skills or the obligations such as to deal with a large number of documents or to meet intensive demands in school, the school principals cannot display instructional leadership features (Gamage, 2006; Mead, 2011). On the other hand, the school principals contribute the quality of the school education by interviewing with the teachers and students about the quality of teaching, giving value their views, appreciating them for achievements and giving positive feedback to the teachers and students as the instructional leaders (Wilkey, 2013). Additionally, they have positive effects on the development of students being a role model, establishing a confidential environment, encouraging professional development of teachers, allocating most of the time to improve teaching, developing high academic standards for school, and supporting teacher relations and cooperation (Balyer, 2013).

2. Literature Review

Increasing demands for accountability have led a few researchers to examine the relationship between principal quality and student outcomes (Krasnoff, 2015). Bastian and Henry (2015) assert that the development of students in the school depends largely on the education, experience and career characteristics of the school principals. Waters, Marzano and McNulty (2003) found that the highly effective principals increase students' test scores up to 10 percentile points on standardized tests in just one year, reduce student absences and suspensions, and improve graduation rates. At the same way, in a study conducted by Leithwood, Seashore, Anderson and Wahlstrom, (2004) it is expressed that the schools in which the principals effectively demonstrate educational leadership roles make an important difference in achieving effective learning. In this context, the school principal is responsible for the maintaining and improving of the teaching quality as well as the other tasks, such as to monitor student behaviors and to implement the training program, effectively (Dhuey and Smith, 2018). In other studies conducted by Sebastian and Allensworth (2012), and Williams (2009) the results show that instructional leadership actions have significant effects on the learning of students in general, but the effects of successful instructional leadership are much more in schools with more difficult conditions. Dhuey and Smith (2018) and Mestry (2017) assert that the effects of the instructional leadership skills of school principals are much greater on the development of the students especially in schools having more problems stemmed from disadvantaged socio-cultural environment.

It is seen that there are a lot of international studies (e.g. Bastian and Henry, 2015; Blasé and Blasé, 1999; Dhuey and Smith, 2018; Leithwood, Seashore, Anderson and Wahlstrom, 2004; Mestry, 2017; Oumer, 2014; Sebastian and Allensworth, 2012; Williams, 2009) about the effects of school principals on the achievements and

development of the students. It is also seen that the national researches focus on the school success (Çelenk, 2003; Çobanoğlu and Badavan, 2017), school effectiveness (Balcı, 1988; Gökçe and Bağçeli-Kahraman, 2010), the quality of school education (Balyer, 2013), the student achievement (Balyer and Gündüz, 2013, Bilge, 2013; Özdemir, 2016). Consequently, it is understood that the studies related to the effects of school principals' administrative skills on the development of the students are limited, in Turkey. It is believed that this study will contribute to the elimination of this deficiency by revealing the effects of the school principals on the development of the students. So, the purpose of this study is to determine the managerial characteristics of the school principals and to reveal the effects on the development of the students. For this purpose, the following questions are sought:

1. What are the views of undergraduates on the personal characteristics of school principals?
2. What are the views of undergraduates on the administrative characteristics of school principals?
3. What are the views of undergraduates on the educational leadership characteristics of school principals?
4. What are the effects of school principals' administrative attitudes and behaviors on the development of students?

3. Method

This research was planned in a qualitative case study model. The case study, is seen as a distinctive approach in search for answers to the scientific questions which aims to investigate the facts that researchers are aware of and at the same time they are not fully understood (Büyüköztürk, Kılıç-Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz and Demirel, 2016; Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2013). The case study is a qualitative approach involving the exchange of experience where the researcher gathers in-detail and in-depth information about an actual situation or phenomenon through observation, interviews and documents (letters, diaries, reports) from multiple sources of knowledge (Creswell, 2014, 2015).

3.1 Study Group

The study group consists of 16 undergraduate students attending to Ordu University Faculty of Education during 2016-2017 academic year. The study group was selected by using typical case sampling method which is one of the purposive sampling methods. The typical sampling method aims to determine the typical, normal and average, in other words, to show or to reveal the normal (Miles and Huberman, 2015, p. 28; Patton, 2014, p. 243). Eight participants were female and 8 were male. All participants were attending teacher education program and they were senior students. Four of them were the graduates attending pre-school teacher education program, four of them primary school, four mathematics, and four science teacher education program. The average age was 22.50.

3.2 Procedure

The research was carried out in four stages respectively. These stages are: (1) identification of the problem, (2) preparation of data collection tools, (3) data collection, and (4) data analysis and interpretation (Mayring, 2011, p.112; Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2013). Details of these stages are presented below:

A. Identification of the problem: The problem was defined in the first step. The students attending undergraduate education were informed about the administrative characteristics of the 'school administrators' which is the main characteristic of the research in the Turkish Education System and School Management course. Then it was asked them whether they could share their positive or negative experiences which they believed to have the greatest impact on their academic and social development related to the attitudes of school principals in school management during their school years. The undergraduates stated that they can share their experiences with the attitudes and behaviors of school principals. A conceptual framework was set up to classify and compare the administrative characteristics of school principals and the impact on the development of students.

B. Preparation of data collection tool: The semi-structured letters were used as a means of collecting data in this study written by undergraduate students to one of their school principals. Unlike magazines, the letters are written to another person with a response expectation. In the words we used in the letter, we try to give ourselves an account by creating the meaning of our experiences, establishing and maintaining the connections between ourselves, our experiences and the experiences of the others (Clandinin and Connelly, 1998, p. 167).

C. Data collection: The data collection process was carried out at six stages, and at the first stage, the form of the letters was determined by the researcher. In the second stage, each participant was asked to think about the school principals who had the greatest impact on their development (positive or negative) in the educational process from primary school to university. In the third stage, it is required that each participant should think about the personal characteristics of the school principal and write these opinions in the form of letters in the first part. In the fourth stage, each participant was asked to think about the administrative characteristics of the school principal and to write the views in the second part of the form. In the fifth stage, each participant was asked to think about the educational leadership qualities of the school principal and to write their views on these features in the third part of the form. In the sixth stage, each participant was asked to think about the effects of the school principals' administrative attitudes and behaviors on their development and write their opinions on these effects in the fourth section of the form. Each interviews lasted about half an hour.

D. Data analysis and interpretation: Since the letters have the document characteristic, each letter was analyzed by using the content analysis technique. As a result of the analysis, the meaning groups were obtained in accordance with the sub problems of the study. Subsequently, main themes and sub-themes related to the sub-problems were determined. The frequency and percentage scores of each sub-theme were calculated

and the participants' opinions related to the sub-problems were presented in tables (Creswell, 2015).

3.3 Validity and Reliability

To ensure the internal validity: data were interpreted considering associated situation, the internal consistency of the sub-themes were supported considering the internal homogeneity and external heterogeneity measures. Besides, the sub-themes were determined based on the theoretical structure, and to ensure internal reliability all findings were presented without comment (Creswell, 2015, pp. 250-254). Additionally, it was applied to the expert opinion in order to verify whether the graduate students' opinions represent sub-themes shown under the main themes. The lists containing the opinions and sub-themes were rendered to two faculty members in educational sciences department. It was asked from the experts that they should compare the opinions with the sub-themes in the lists, and then the matches were compared. It was applied the formula 'Reliability= Consensus/ (Consensus + Dissidence) × 100' to determine the reliability of the coding (Miles and Huberman, 1994, p. 64). The agreement between the three coders was calculated as $113 / (113 + 4) \times 100 = 96.58$. In addition, the research model, study group, data collection tool and data analysis processes were given in detail to ensure the external validity of the study. Besides, the procedure was specified, in detail for each sections to ensure the external reliability of the study: the procedures including data collection, data analysis, consolidation and presentation of the results, the topic and method.

4. Findings and Interpretation

In this section, the findings related to the first sub-problem of the study are given. Two main themes were identified regarding the personal characteristics of the school principals: positive personal characteristics, and negative personal characteristics. For the positive characteristics main theme 22 sub-themes [$\eta=22$, $f=41$] were determined, and 17 sub-themes [$\eta=17$, $f= 39$] were designated for the negative characteristics main theme.

The frequencies and percentages of the participant opinions on personal characteristics of the school principals are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Personal Characteristics of the School Principals (N=16)

Positive Personal Characteristics	f	%	Negative Personal Characteristics	f	%
Good-humored	4	9.80	Authoritarian	6	15.30
Neat	4	9.80	Punitive	5	12.70
Sympathetic	3	7.30	Normative	4	10.30
Fair	3	7.30	Strict	4	10.30
Tolerant	2	4.90	Distant	3	7.70
Respectful	2	4.90	Reactive	3	7.70
Responsible	2	4.90	Prejudiced	2	5.10

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Sympathizer	2	4.90	Nervous	2	5.10
Humanist	2	4.90	Biased	2	5.10
Prudent	2	4.90	Dour	1	2.60
Charismatic	2	4.90	Competitive	1	2.60
Trustworthy	2	4.90	Grabby	1	2.60
Concerned	2	4.90	Disorderly	1	2.60
Tactful	1	2.40	Careless	1	2.60
Strong-minded	1	2.40	Impatient	1	2.60
Cheerful	1	2.40	Inconsistent	1	2.60
Sensitive	1	2.40	Intolerant	1	2.60
Polite	1	2.40			
Spiritual	1	2.40			
Well-groomed	1	2.40			
Helpful	1	2.40			
Warm	1	2.40			
Total	41	100	Total	39	100

In Table 1, it is seen that the most frequent positive personal characteristics of the school principals are 'good-humored' [$\eta=4$, 9.8%], 'neat' [$\eta=4$, 9.8%], 'sympathetic' [$\eta=3$, 7.3%], and 'fair' [$\eta=3$, 7.3%]. The most frequent negative personal characteristics of the school principals are 'authoritarian' [$\eta=6$, 15.3%], 'punitive' [$\eta=5$, 12.7%], 'normative' [$\eta=4$, 10.3%], 'strict' [$\eta=4$, 10.3%], 'distant' [$\eta=3$, 7.7%], and 'reactive' [$\eta=3$, 7.7%].

In this section, the findings related to the second sub-problem of the study are given.

Two main themes were identified regarding the administrative characteristics of the school principals: positive characteristics, and negative characteristics. For the positive characteristics main theme 24 sub-themes [$\eta=24$, $f=44$] were determined, and 21 sub-themes [$\eta=21$, $f=36$] were designated related to the negative characteristics main theme.

The frequencies and percentages of the participant opinions on administrative characteristics of the school principals are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Administrative Characteristics of the School Principals (N=16)

Positive	f	%	Negative	f	%
Exhibits a solution-focused management	4	9.10	Exhibits punitive attitude	4	11.0
Creates positive school culture	3	6.90	Exhibits extreme restrictive attitude	3	8.20
Makes staff feel valuable	3	6.90	Exhibits a distant attitude	3	8.20
Listens everybody as carefully as	3	6.90	Behaves official	3	8.20
Committed to teamwork	2	4.50	Focuses on external appearance	2	5.60
Behaves responsible	2	4.50	Behaves prejudiced	2	5.60
Exhibits fair management	2	4.50	Focuses on deficiencies	2	5.60
Makes work fondly	2	4.50	Inadequate communication skills	2	5.60
Embraces school	2	4.50	Makes strict supervision in school	2	5.60
Exhibits a polite attitude	2	4.50	Exhibits authoritarian management	2	5.60
Exhibits an effective management	2	4.50	Advises constantly	1	2.80
Creates a safe school climate	2	4.50	Behaves indifferently	1	2.80
Strives improvement of the school	2	4.50	Behaves non-human oriented attitude	1	2.80
Creates school culture based on the rules	2	4.50	Not open to innovation	1	2.80
Succeeds in school development	2	4.50	Behaves partial	1	2.80

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Behaves fair to students	1	2.30	A non-merited school principal	1	2.80
Creates a democratic school environment	1	2.30	An untrusted school principal	1	2.80
Takes risk	1	2.30	Behaves with extreme reactive	1	2.80
Exhibits a constant attitude	1	2.30	Insufficient coordination	1	2.80
Makes participative decisions in school	1	2.30	Ineffective on the staff	1	2.80
Works planned	1	2.30	Insensitive to the school problems	1	2.80
Exhibits student-centered management	1	2.30			
Exhibits supportive attitudes	1	2.30			
Takes care of everyone in school	1	2.30			
Total	44	100	Total	36	100

In Table 2, it is seen that the most frequent positive administrative characteristics of school principals are 'exhibits a solution-focused management' [$\eta=4$, 9.1%], 'creates positive school culture' [$\eta=3$, 6.9%], 'makes staff feel valuable' [$\eta=3$, 6.9%], and 'listens everybody as carefully as' [$\eta=3$, 6.9%]. The most frequent negative administrative characteristics are 'exhibits punitive attitude' [$\eta=4$, 11%], 'exhibits extreme restrictive attitude' [$\eta=3$, 8.2%], 'exhibits a distant attitude' [$\eta=3$, 8.2%], and 'behaves official' [$\eta=3$, 8.2%].

In this section, the findings related to the third sub-problem of the study are given. Only one main theme was identified regarding the instructional leadership characteristics of the school principals: instructional leadership. 20 sub-themes [$\eta=20$, $f=40$] were determined under the instructional leadership main theme.

The frequencies and percentages of the participant opinions on instructional leadership characteristics of the school principals are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Instructional Leadership Characteristics of the School Principals (N=16)

Instructional Leadership Characteristics	f	%
Focuses on educational success of the school	5	12.50
Motivates to learn	4	10.0
Cares all students	4	10.0
Establishes an effective learning environment	4	10.0
Leads teaching	4	10.0
Appreciates to the success of students	3	7.50
Provides continuity of learning in school	2	5.00
Gives positive feedback to students	2	5.00
Evaluates the learning in school as process-driven	1	2.50
Cooperates with parents to increase learning	1	2.50
Analyzes test results correctly	1	2.50
Encourages student-centered education	1	2.50
Engrains in students the happiness of learning	1	2.50
Gains students a planned work habit	1	2.50
Gives students positive energy	1	2.50
Develops students multi-faceted	1	2.50
Supports self-sacrificing movements of students	1	2.50
Supports social activities	1	2.50
Communicates effectively with the students	1	2.50
Works devotedly to increase learning	1	2.50
Total	40	100

According to Table 3, the most frequent instructional leadership characteristics of the school principals are 'focuses on educational success of the school' [$\eta=5$, 12.5%], 'motivates to learn' [$\eta=4$, 10%], 'cares all students' [$\eta=4$, 10%], 'establishes an effective learning environment' [$\eta=4$, 10%], and 'leads to teaching' [$\eta=4$, 10%].

In this section, the findings related to the fourth sub-problem of the study are given. Two main themes were identified regarding the effects of administrative characteristics on the development of the students: positive effects, and negative effects. 17 sub-themes [$\eta=17$, $f=42$] were determined by considering positive effects main theme. And 18 sub-themes [$\eta=18$, $f=38$] were designated for the negative effects main theme. The frequency and percentages of opinions about the effects of school principals' administrative attitudes on the development of students are given Table 4.

Table 4: The Effects of the School Principals' Administrative Attitudes (N=16)

Positive Effects	f	%	Negative Effects	f	%
Self-confidence	6	14.30	To feel fear	7	18.40
Self-respect	5	11.90	Violence	3	7.90
To feel precious	4	9.50	Humiliation	3	7.90
Gratitude	3	7.10	Lack of self-confidence	3	7.90
To feel determined	3	7.10	Timidity	3	7.90
Courage	2	4.80	To feel ashamed	2	5.30
Humanism	2	4.80	Feeling of worthlessness	2	5.30
To be role-model	2	4.80	Failure perception	2	5.30
Awareness	2	4.80	Anger	2	5.30
To be fair	2	4.80	Lack of motivation	2	5.30
Tolerance	2	4.80	To feel tensioned	2	5.30
Love	2	4.80	Result oriented	1	2.60
Regular study	2	4.80	Decrease of life energy	1	2.60
Responsibility	2	4.80	Study inefficiently	1	2.60
Learning to learn	1	2.30	Feel like inarticulate	1	2.60
Communication skills	1	2.30	Comparison with others	1	2.60
Self-esteem	1	2.30	Disappointment	1	2.60
			Hopelessness	1	2.60
Total	42	100	Total	38	100

The administrative attitudes of school principals affect positively students' development. According to Table 4, the most frequent feelings of students are 'self-confidence' [$\eta=6$, 14.3%], 'self-respect' [$\eta=5$, 11.9%], 'to feel precious' [$\eta=4$, 9.5%], 'gratitude' [$\eta=3$, 7.1%], and 'to feel determined' [$\eta=3$, 7.1%]. In addition, the school principals' administrative attitudes affect negatively development of the students. The most frequent feelings of the students are 'to feel fear' [$\eta=7$, 18.4%], 'violence' [$\eta=3$, 7.9%], 'humiliation' [$\eta=3$, 7.9%], 'lack of self-confidence' [$\eta=3$, 7.9%], and 'timidity' [$\eta=3$, 7.9%].

5. Conclusion

In this research, aiming to reveal the administrative characteristics exhibited by the school principals and the effects on the development of the students, the findings indicated that the school principals display positive and negative personal characteristics. The positive personal characteristics of school principals were good-humored, neat, sympathetic, fair, tolerant, respectful, responsible, sympathizer, humanistic, prudent, charismatic, trustworthy and concerned. The findings reveal that the good-humored, neat, sympathetic and fair administrators show a solution-focused management, create a positive school culture and appreciate the employees and listen them carefully. Similar findings are seen in previous studies. In a study conducted by Fook and Sidhu (2009), the excellent principals have positive personal values such as the modeling and promotion of respect for individuals, fairness and equality, caring for the well-being and whole development of students and staff, integrity and honesty. The negative personal characteristics exhibited by school principals were authoritarian, punitive, normative, strict, distant, reactive, prejudiced, biased, and nervous. School administrators who display authoritarian, punitive, normative and strict attitudes tend to distant from students by overly adhering to the formal rules or punish them, frequently. Similarly, in a study conducted by Welch and Payne (2010) the results show that it is widely acknowledged that in American schools -urban public schools in particular- the student discipline is defined and managed with an increasingly punitive approach therefore, the school administrators exhibit authoritarian, punitive, normative and strict attitudes.

The participants stated that the school principals exhibit positive administrative characteristics. The most frequent positive administrative characteristics of the school principals were to exhibit a solution-focused management, to create positive school culture, to make staff feel valuable, and to listen everybody as carefully as. The results show that these features have positive effects on the development of students. Similarly, Bastian and Henry (2015), Branch, Hanushek and Rivkin (2012) indicated that the principal's quality affects student achievement, and quality of education in schools. The participants also stated that the school principals exhibit negative administrative characteristics. The most frequent negative administrative characteristics were to exhibit punitive attitude, to exhibit extreme restrictive attitude, to exhibit a distant attitude, and behaves official. Similarly, in the studies conducted by Hilarski (2004) and Hirschfield (2008) the findings show that in the schools where the principals' display punitive, extreme restrictive, and distant attitudes, the disciplinary problems increase, and the achievements of students decrease.

The results show that the most frequent instructional leadership characteristics of school principals were to focus on educational success of the school, to motivate to learn, to care all students, to establish an effective learning environment, to lead to teaching, and to appreciate success of students. These leadership features affect positively the development of the students. Similarly, in the studies conducted by Leithwood, Seashore, Anderson and Wahlstrom (2004), Sebastian and Allensworth

(2012), Waters, Marzano and McNulty (2003) and Williams (2009) the findings show that the instructional leadership actions have significant effects on the achievements of students, in general.

The results also show that the administrative attitudes of school principals affect positively students' development. The positive attitudes of school principals ensure the feelings on students such as self-confidence, self-respect, to feel precious, gratitude, awareness, love and courage. In addition, the school principals engrain in students to feel determined, to be fair regular study, responsibility, tolerance, and humanism being role-model to them. Similarly, Day and Sammons (2013) and Özdemir (2016) assert that the instructional/pedagogical leadership has play an important role promoting better academic outcomes for students. In addition, the school principals' negative administrative attitudes cause disruptive results on the development of students. These attitudes ensure the feelings such as fear, violence, humiliation, and lack of self-confidence, lack of motivation, timidity, anger, worthlessness, ashamed, tensioned, and failure perception. Similarly, in the studies conducted by Gregory, Skiba and Noguera (2010), Hilarski (2004), Hirschfield (2008), and Welch and Payne (2010) the findings show that the school principals' negative administrative attitudes hinder academic and social development of the students, and cause the disruptive behaviours displayed by the students.

6. Recommendations

Consequently, the findings show that the students are affected school principals' both personal and administrative characteristics. The positive attitudes of school principals ensure the feelings on students such as self-confidence, self-respect, to feel precious, gratitude, awareness, love and courage. Based on these results it can be suggested that the principals should be selected, trained and assigned considering personal characteristic. The school principals should display good-humored, neat, sympathetic, fair, tolerant, respectful, and responsible attitudes in schools. In addition, the negative attitudes ensure the feelings such as fear, violence, humiliation, and lack of self-confidence, lack of motivation, timidity, anger, worthlessness, and ashamed. Therefore, the principals should avoid to display punitive, normative, strict, distant, reactive, prejudiced, biased, and nervous attitudes. According to the findings, the most frequent instructional leadership characteristics of school principals were to focus on educational success of the school, to motivate to learn, to care all students, to establish an effective learning environment, to lead to teaching, and to appreciate success of students. Based on the results it can be suggest that the school principals should exhibit a solution-focused management, create positive school culture, make staff feel valuable, and should listen everybody as carefully as. In addition, they should motivate students to learn, care all students, establish an effective learning environment, lead them to teaching and appreciate the success of students. The current study was planned as a qualitative case study model. Further studies can be planned by using different model and conducted on different sampling groups.

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